

APPLE MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN STORAGE OF EXPORT VARIETIES OF FRUIT

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Abstract. In the article, the method of increasing the shelf life of apples depending on the type was created on the basis of the environmentally safe natural biopolymer chitosan and its compositions with organic acids, and the mechanisms of the influence of the drugs on the shelf life of the fruit varieties were studied. The relationship between modern technologies of fruit preservation is analyzed. It has been shown that the optimal environment and the concentration of preparations and relative humidity are important in the storage of apple fruits.

Keywords: export, apple varieties, chitosan, biopolymer, acetic acid, succinic acid, glyceric acid, antibacterial, antimicrobial, controlled atmosphere, controlled gas environment.

In the last 10 years, the development of fruit products in the world is increasing significantly. 120 kg of fruit is enough for the annual consumption of the world's population. In the leading developed countries, the main attention is paid to providing the population with ecologically safe food products. In these countries, great attention is being paid to the use of preparations obtained from natural products, abandoning chemical synthetic means in the processes of food storage and processing [1, 2].

In the world experience, there are various technologies in the process of preserving fruits and vegetables. For example, the following technologies are used for creating a gas environment and for long-term storage of fruits in a controlled atmosphere:

- ULO (Ultra Low Oxygen) - storage in the chamber with extremely low oxygen content (less than 1-1.5%);
- RCA (Rapid Controlled Atmosphere) - technology for rapid reduction of oxygen concentration;
- ILOS (Initial Low Oxygen Stress) - an ultra-fast decrease in the oxygen level in the chamber in a short time;
- LECA (Low Ethylene Controlled Atmosphere) - technology to reduce the level of ethylene in the chamber;
- DCA (Dynamic Controlled Atmosphere) - dynamically controlled atmosphere;
- CO₂ shock treatment - shock technology by increasing the concentration of carbon dioxide gas (up to 30%) [3].

Modified atmosphere storage technology is widely used. A gas environment is created with a polyethylene film gas-selective membrane, raw material respiration (O_2 absorption, CO_2 release) or barrier-type polymer film packages .

In addition, the use of some antiseptic substances among storage methods has a negative effect on human health, as it results in long-term storage of fruits.

the creation of "edible" polymer coatings on the surface of vegetables and fruits. The antibacterial and antimicrobial properties of chitosan have been widely described in the literature. Covering the surface of fruits with semi-permeable chitosan coating endogenous gases (CO_2 , O_2 and ethylene) changes the level, prevents aerobic respiration, which represents the bacterio- and fungistatic effect of this biopolymer.

apples were treated with the above preparations, it was observed that their water loss decreased by 20-40% depending on the variety .

According to world standards, new generation drugs must meet the following requirements:

- highly effective effect;
- economic efficiency;
- environmental safety.

These requirements increase the relevance of creating biocompatible, biodegradable natural polymers, including preparations based on chitosan [4-9].

The goal of our research is to create preparations with the characteristic of increasing the shelf life of fruits based on chitosan synthesized by the method of deacetylation from silkworm cocoon, which is an ecologically clean natural raw material. To solve this problem , the use of the optimal composition of the polymer system was chosen: chitosan - organic acid - water-based compositions were made by covering the surface of the fruit .

Used materials and research methods:

In our research, analytically pure chitosan with an average molecular weight of M_n - 25,000, a degree of deacetylation of 85 mol%, and acetic, lactic and dibasic carboxylic acids were used [10].

During storage of fruits and vegetables, they were processed with chitosan and its derivatives using solutions and complexes based on edible organic acids (acetic acid, succinic acid, ascorbic acid, glycyrrhizic acid and others). For experiments, burnt fruits and vegetables were stored in the "Lider" series refrigerator, where one ton of product is stored, according to generally accepted standards .

Scientific researches were conducted on the export apple varieties "Farangiz", "Fuji Kuki", "Golden delicacies" and "Grain Smith".

The USAID "Development of the Value Chain in Agriculture" (AVC) project of the International Development Agency of the United States of America, the shelf life of the above apple varieties is set at 7-12 months depending on the variety.

Working solutions were prepared by dissolving 0.2% chitosan solution in aqueous solutions of organic acids in the ratio of 1:1, 1:2 and 2:1 for 24 hours at 25°C.

Polymer coating of the surface of fruits with pH 6.5-6.7 processing, each fruit was immersed in a polymer solution for 1 minute , and then dried in the open air.

Distilled water was used as a control, the treated fruits were weighed and stored in a refrigerator at +3°C and 90-95% relative humidity.

Table 1

Export chapter apple varieties and their effect on fruit weight loss, Temperature $t = +1+3^{\circ}\text{C}$. Relative humidity $q = 90-95\%$. Weight loss %.

T/r	Processing indicators	Shelf life of apple varieties, months			
		Farangiz, 8 months	Fuji cookie, 7 months	Golden delicacies , 12 months	Grain smith , 12 months
1	Control	7.3	8.7	8.7	8.45
2	XZ 0.1%, SK 0.1% (1:1)	3.3	3.3	5	4.6
3	XZ 0.2%, SK 0.2% (1:2)	3	3	4	4.2
4	XZ 0.2% Qk 0.25%, (1:1)	3.2	3.2	4.45	4.7
5	XZ 0.1% Qk 0.1% (1:1)	3.1	3.1	4.5	4.75
6	XZ 0.1%, Gk 0.01% (1:1)	3	3	3.9	4.3
7	XZ 0.2%, Gk 0.01% (1:1)	3	3	4	4.4

Chitosan-XZ, Acetic acid-SK, Succinic acid-Qk, Glyceric acid-Gl

Fruits nutritional value was assessed visually and organoleptically. The results of processing were expressed as a percentage of the weight of damaged fruits at the end of the experiment to the total weight of processed fruits (percentage of loss), (Table 1).

As a result of the conducted experiments and organoleptic observation and analysis, preparations with optimal concentration for seed fruits, depending on their variety , were isolated and used in further research. The following table shows the preparations used in the preservation of seed fruits and the results obtained

Summing up from the above results, it can be said that the effectiveness of preparations based on the composition of chitosan with acetic acid in the preservation of "Farangiz" variety was observed. In this case, it was found that the efficiency is 2.4 to 2.8 times higher than the control . It was observed in experiments that the effectiveness of chitosan glyceric acid complex is 2.4 times higher .

The results of the experiment show that in the preservation of the fruits of "Fuji Kuki" apple, which is newly regionalized in Uzbekistan, when treated with preparations based on chitosan and acetic acid, the efficiency of the preservation period was 1.7 to 1.8 times higher. In the case of chitosan citric acid, up to 2 times efficiency

was achieved. As can be seen from the results presented in the table above, it was found that the influence of chitosan and its preparation with organic acids on the shelf life of various concentrations is not very high (from 0.3 to 0.6 times). It can be concluded from this that the given preparations have different effects on biological processes in fruits during storage .

The compositions of 0.1% and 0.2% solutions of chitosan with 0.1% and 0.2% solutions of acetic acid for the "Golden Delicious" variety have high efficiency and effectively affect biological processes occurring in fruits . Their efficiency is 1.8 to 2.2 times higher than the control. It was observed that the results obtained in the remaining preparations were on average 0.3 and 0.6 times higher . In high- concentration solutions of chitosan , in 1% and 2% solutions of 0.5% acetic acid, the storage time was 2 times less than the control, and a negative effect on product quality was observed, similar results were observed in 0.2% and 0.1% solutions of chitosan with ascorbic acid. It was also observed in preparations made from 0.1% and 0.25% solutions . When treated with the above preparations, the highest efficiency was found to be 0.5 to 0.8 times higher than the control when treated with various concentrations of chitosan treated with acetic acid . This is due to the fact that the second ripening period of this variety is short and the skin is thin . The composition of chitosan prepared in high concentration of acetic acid, as well as preparations based on chitosan ascorbic acid, had a negative effect on the shelf life of apples. This is explained by the fact that the compositions made with a high concentration solution of chitosan and ascorbic acid have a foaming effect on the thin skin of the apple .

The effect of the preparations listed in the table for the "Grain Smith" variety is chitosan acetic acid in small concentrations (0.1-0.2%) based on solutions of acetic acid (0.1-0.2%) and chitosan with 0.01% glyceric acid. Complexes obtained in different proportions have an effective effect on the shelf life and quality of the fruit. It was found in experiments that the efficiency increased from 1.5 to 2 times . The results obtained with other preparations were found to have almost no change in efficiency or a negative effect on shelf life, especially in solutions of high concentration of chitosan, as well as in compositions of chitosan and ascorbic acid . We believe that the reason for this is the high sensitivity of this type of apple to reagents [11, 12].

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